

**SPECIFIC ISSUES REGARDING LANGUAGE REFLECTION OF
NATIONAL CUSTOMS, TRADITIONS, AND HABITS IN THE PERIOD
OF GLOBALIZATION**

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ANNOTATION: This article discusses issues related to the linguistic reflection of national customs, traditions, and habits in the field of philology during the era of globalization. These issues are clarified with examples and substantiated by analyses. The unique features of these reflections are also analyzed.

Keywords: national tradition, traditions and customs, ethnic idiom, breaking bread, ethnographic lexicon.

Introduction. Language reflects the lifestyle of people, their surrounding nature, societal phenomena, interpersonal relations, and all facets of human existence against the backdrop of their culture. It preserves and conveys these aspects from generation to generation. Therefore, language plays a decisive role in shaping individuals, national character, ethnic communities, people, and nations. The national characteristics embedded in a language layer encompass values, social ethics, and attitudes toward the world, people, and other nations. These aspects have always drawn the attention of linguists and foreign language learners alike.

Literature Review. “Language is a mirror of culture, reflecting not only the real world and conditions surrounding humans but also a nation’s social self-awareness, mentality, national character, lifestyle, traditions, customs, ethics, value systems, and worldview.” [1:14]

The rich Uzbek language, embodying the spirit of the nation and considered a hallmark of our national identity and existence, is also a repository of the cultural traditions and customs of the people.

From childhood, individuals learn their native language along with their culture, gradually comprehending both. The intricate nuances of a people's culture, encompassing their understanding of the world and individual identity, are uniquely expressed in their language. Linguocultural analysis, which delves into the factors forming these subtleties within a language, increasingly attracts the attention of linguists.

“A significant portion of information and perceptions about the world comes to people through linguistic channels. Consequently, individuals live more within a world of intellectual, spiritual, and social concepts created for these needs rather than the physical world of objects and things. The majority of information is received through words, and a person's success in society depends on how effectively they use language, not just in terms of speech culture but also in understanding linguistic intricacies.” [2:3]

Research Methodology. Language not only reflects the world and culture but also serves as a bridge for transferring these across generations. Hence, an individual's personality, national character, worldview, and attitudes toward their surroundings and values are vividly expressed in their use of language and linguistic units. A linguistic community uses language to reflect its national-cultural uniqueness, lifestyle, and the essence of its traditions and customs. This is achieved through linguistic units such as terms, phraseologies, and idioms that reveal national mentality.

For instance, the phrase “Girls, let's apply o'sma* carries aesthetic significance only for native speakers within a particular cultural context. For others from different cultures, this expression might seem incomprehensible since not all women worldwide apply o'sma (a traditional eyebrow enhancer). In Uzbek

households, women have historically grown o'sma for cosmetic purposes. This concept, ingrained in national identity, is evidenced in proverbs and songs:

- O'sma fades, but eyebrows remain.
- “Let those who see you, want to see you again,” alla.
- “Who is this girl?” they should ask, alla.
- “Let me braid your hair finely, alla.”
- “Let me apply o'sma to your eyebrows, alla.”

Idioms are akin to carefully measured spices in speech — without them, discourse would lack vibrancy, sharpness, and distinctiveness.

Words and terms associated with rituals, traditions, customs, and beliefs created over centuries form a distinct lexical group in a language, commonly referred to as ethnographic lexicon. For instance, N. Mirzaev's Explanatory Dictionary of Uzbek Ethnographic Terms includes over 1,300 words and phrases related to ceremonies, customs, and traditions.

Analysis and Results. “Part of the ethnographic lexicon derives from repurposing everyday words with new, additional meanings beyond their original sense. For example, words like tovoq (platter), uloq (game), tugun (bundle), yirtish (ripping), aytimchi (pledge), yetti (seven), qirq (forty), and yil (year) take on specialized meanings in the ethnographic context.” [4:3]

For instance, the term yirtish in Samarkand districts refers to the practice of distributing cloth wrapped around tea during funeral ceremonies. Similarly, breaking bread (non sindirmoq) in its literal sense means to divide bread but as an idiom, it symbolizes a pre-wedding custom signifying commitment and unity between two families.

Conclusion and Recommendations. To conclude, language is not merely a result of culture but a necessary condition for its existence. It serves as the foundation of traditions, customs, and norms that define cultural practices.

Language, therefore, is essential for preserving and transmitting these cultural elements across generations.

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